

Effectiveness of Marketing Strategies in the Midst of Pandemic in the Customers of Milk tea Shops in Molino II of Bacoor City Cavite

¹Ma. Rhodora E. Velasco, ²Sarah Servano, ³Princess Joy A. Buenviaje, MSBA-HRM

^{1,2} Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management

³ Adviser

DE LA SALLE UNIVERSITY – DASMARINAS

College of Tourism and Hospitality Management

Hotel & Restaurant Management Department

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6613808>

Published Date: 04-June-2022

Abstract: The aim of the study is to know the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the midst of COVID - 19 pandemic in the customers of milktea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, Cavite. The researchers chose Molino II of Bacoor City in Cavite because it is the province's gateway to Manila, whereby lots of micro-businesses are established, so it's an ideal location for the study. The paper adopted descriptive type of quantitative research design and surveyed (100) one hundred selected participants that was willing to cooperate with this study using google forms. Data collected were analyzed by using statistical methods which are; frequency and percentage, measures of central tendency or mean and chi-square, it is to have a clear conclusion. The result of the survey will reach the objectives of this study. The collected data analysis results including the 4ps; Product, Price, Place and Promotions shows how effective the marketing strategies in the midst pandemic to the said businesses.

Keywords: Marketing Strategies - A strategy for promoting and selling a products or services COVID - 19 - It is an acute respiratory illness in human, it is a virus that can be transmitted through an infected person.

Micro Businesses - A type of a small business 4 Ps - Marketing mix of 4 Ps; Product, Price, Promotion and Place, these are the key factors in terms of marketing products or services.

1. INTRODUCTION

The hospitality industry plays an essential role in the global economy. As the Covid-19 continuously spread worldwide, the global economy began to fall causing financial losses. The restaurant industry is the worst affected sector caused by the Covid-19 pandemic; thus, a lot of changes are needed to implement to avoid a high risk of spreading the said virus.

The SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19 viral RNA was reported to be detected last January 30, 2020. The said virus triggered the area and began to spread swiftly. The government was alarmed which caused a lockdown in the Greater Manila Area and neighbouring provinces. Many families were affected by the pandemic and results of the increased community quarantine; businesses were forced to close temporarily; labor workforces were forced to stop more so resign because of the uncertainty of the situation. Now that the government has eased the enforcement of quarantines, milk tea shops are back in the business where they can accept dine-in customers.

Milk tea shops are a popular business to start nowadays. New build Milk tea shops are showing and it became popular in the business industry. But suddenly the pandemic changed everything, not just the businesses but also the customers. Milk tea shops face many challenges, such as decreased consumer demand, sales, and employees. A new strategy for marketing to clients has arisen as a result of this major change and the term "new normal" comes a new way to market to customers. According to Kappel (2020), The term "new normal" is the current concept of life as well as strategies to guard against the coronavirus, it includes the change of behavior due to fear of contagion of the virus. This means people are careful and

protect themselves to avoid spreading the virus. Because of this, it affects the small business in the industry such as milk tea shops.

As stated by Purwanto (2021), he reveals that the marketing strategy is a way to win a sustainable competitive advantage for companies that sell goods or services. Customers can be drawn to a recovery marketing strategy during the Covid-19 pandemic if it is segmented, targeted, and positioned correctly. Other supporting elements for running a firm easily and effectively include promotion through online media, collaborations, great service, and rewards.

According to the Department of Trade and Industry, dine-in restaurants and fast-food companies are authorized to operate at 50% capacity in regions under modified general community quarantine (MGCQ), but only under strict conditions (DTI). With the easing of restrictions and movement for areas under Modified General Community Quarantine (MGCQ) status, the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF) has approved a minimum health protocol that dine-in restaurants and fast-food chains must implement and observe before their reopening in two weeks. In this sense, Milk tea shops can operate and take dine-in orders for a limit of 50% capacity only and with safety precautions.

The researchers conduct the study to evaluate the effectiveness of the marketing strategies of milk tea shops in the midst of the pandemic. Thus, the goals of this study are to know what is the perception of the customers towards the marketing strategies of the business, to determine which marketing strategies are effective to use, and to learn what the customers' expectation will reach their satisfaction. This study can help those who are starting small businesses such as milk tea shops to know furthermore about marketing strategies' effectiveness in the new normal. It highlights the change of marketing strategies to fulfill customers' needs and wants. Furthermore, it intends to make recommendations based on the findings that can be used as a reference by the researchers in the future.

Background of the study

A market strategy is long-term planning for reaching the consumer's perspective which can turn them into the customer of their products and services. It includes the set of goals and overall direction of the business marketing which will show the specific actions you will construct to apply your marketing strategy. It also describes the process of how businesses can comprehend their markets and methods of affecting profitable customer action.

Kanyan et. al (2016) said that foodservice outlets are establishments that provide meals and snacks for on-the-spot consumption. Commercial foodservice facilities accounted for most food-away-from-home purchases. Full-service restaurants, quick food restaurants, caterers, some cafeterias, and other businesses that prepare, serve and sell food to the general public for profit fall under this category. There are various aspects of food service that distinguish it from other types of product production. This distinction has an impact on manufacturing and service delivery decisions. The first trait is that food demand is highest at mealtimes such as breakfast, lunch, and dinner. There are slack periods in between these peak demand periods. Second, food consumption can fluctuate depending on the time of year and competitive events, requiring production to be adjusted accordingly. Food production and service are labour-intensive industries that require both expert and unskilled workers. Because food is perishable, it must be treated with care before, during, and after preparation. Furthermore, menus may vary daily, causing production to fluctuate. These qualities make it difficult to schedule people and production, which can lead to staffing issues as well as excessive labour and food expenditures.

"The Philippine Competition Act (PCA) or R.A. 10667 is the primary competition policy of the Philippines for promoting and protecting the competitive market." It will secure customers' interests while still preserving the efficiency of the marketplace's competitiveness. It is a game-changing piece of legislation that is projected to strengthen consumer protection while also assisting in the acceleration of investment and job creation in the country, in line with the national government's goal of more inclusive economic growth. This law's enforcement will help to ensure that markets are open and free, addressing anticompetitive business practices while preserving a competitive environment where businesses may compete on the quality of their work. A competitive market is one in which there are several buyers and sellers, lowering market prices and providing consumers with more options. A highly competitive market stimulates efficiency and innovation, as well as pushing enterprises to achieve their full potential.

The research is all about the effectiveness of market strategies in the midst of pandemics in the Customers of Milk tea Shops in Molino II of Bacoor City Cavite and also covers the marketing mix which is the 4ps: product, price, place, and promotion. Researchers chose Molino Bacoor City Cavite as their location in research because it is near the subdivisions where there are customers that experienced the service quality of the selected Milk tea Shops. Researchers came up with

this research topic because they noticed that some were forced to close because of pandemic and their market strategy did not work. On the other side, many Milk tea Shops opened because of their advantage in the middle of the pandemic that makes their market strategy works.

It is all about positioning your company to meet the needs of your target market when it comes to marketing. When it comes to promoting your products and services, there are four key aspects to consider. They are known as the marketing four Ps. First is the "product" where you find the right product that will satisfy the needs of your customer. The second is "price" which shows the product's right value. The third is the "place" which refers to the customers who may purchase the right goods at the right price in the right location. The last one is the "promotion" which informing potential customers about the product's availability, price, and location.

Theoretical Framework

Marketing Mix Theoretical Aspect proposed by Margarita Isoraite (June 2016), implies the idea that the marketing mix is one of the key objectives of the marketing mix elements for creating objectives and marketing budget measures. The four Ps of marketing is the most important aspects of selling a product or service. They are goods or services' product, pricing, place, and promotion. Companies utilize the 4 Ps to figure out what their customers want from them, how their product or service fulfils or fails to satisfy those demands, how their product or service is viewed in the world, how they differentiate themselves from their competitors, and how they engage with their customers. There is a constant change of environment. For marketers to continuously earn a profit, effective marketing mix management will allow marketers to produce a combination of these 4Ps to achieve the desired goals.

Conceptual Framework

The research paradigm demonstrates a figure for a better understanding of the study. It identifies the input, process, and output (IPO) of the relationship between variables.

The first box is the input. It shows the (1) demographic profile of the respondents in terms of: age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, income/allowance, frequency of visit. (2) The perception in marketing strategies in the midst of pandemic in terms of: product, price, place, and promotion.

The second box is the process that shows how the researchers will gather the data wherein the researchers will use survey questionnaires via Google forms.

The third box is the output, which will be the proposed marketing mix strategies for the Milk tea Shops in the Midst of the pandemic.

Research Paradigm

Figure 1: The Research Paradigm

Statement of the Problem

This study will evaluate the Effectiveness of Marketing Strategies in the Midst of the Pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino Area of Bacoor City Cavite as perceived by the customer respondents.

Specifically, this will seek the answer to the following question:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 civil status;
 - 1.4 educational attainment;
 - 1.5 income /allowance;
 - 1.6 Frequency of visit; and
2. What is the level of the perception of the customers on the marketing mix strategies components as to:
 - 2.1 Product;
 - 2.2 Price;
 - 2.3 Place; and
 - 2.4 Promotion
3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their perception of the effectiveness of marketing strategies during Pandemic in Milk tea Shops in Molino Area of Bacoor City Cavite?
4. What effective marketing strategies can be recommended while in the midst of a pandemic to the Milk tea shops in Molino area of Bacoor City Cavite?

Statement of Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the profile and the effects of marketing strategies in the midst of the pandemic of the respondents.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature and studies that the researcher found related to the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the midst of pandemic in the milk tea shops. This part contains facts and information on the research problem at hand, it also states some explanations and logical connections within the previous research and present work.

During COVID-19 Pandemic, in terms of the Food Industry, defining your target market, working place, and prioritizing health protocols are always the first factors to be considered. Talking about "New Protocols", it started when the COVID-19 Pandemic arrived in the Philippines. "It is a research finding that shows the recovery marketing strategy during the Covid-19 pandemic that can be done through segmenting, targeting, and positioning to attract consumers. In addition, the supporting factors to run entrepreneurship efficiently and effectively include the use of promotions through online media, partnerships, excellent service, and awards." Businesses have to recover and create new marketing strategies which support the study Purwanto (2021).

Morgan et. al (2019) said in their article that, "Marketing strategy lies at the conceptual heart of the strategic marketing field. It is also central to marketing practice and the area within which many of the most pressing challenges for marketers arise." They use a new conceptualization of the domain of the marketing strategy as a lens and assess the current state of the marketing strategy research. They uncover important challenges and new knowledge that may be highly relevant in marketing strategy.

Proctor (2020) said that marketing is all about meeting the demands and needs of customers while also assisting in the attainment of an organization's goals. Organizations are more likely to succeed if they pay attention to customer requests and needs. To attain their goals in the marketplace organizations, of course, have to compete with one another, they must

also serve the needs of their clients. They must meet their customers' needs at least as well as their competition. Meeting customers' wants and needs will make the business successful because it would be great feedback for the reputation of the business especially for the micro-businesses that are starting to grow and making an image in the business industry.

Moorman, C., Kirby, L., McCarthy, T., And Shkil, B. (2020) states that COVID-19 has driven marketers to evaluate how they will promote and interact with customers. And the marketing strategies that were formulated and implemented during the COVID-19 will provide significant long-term opportunities for their business. To achieve the "long-term opportunities for their business" the firm should know and prioritize customer satisfaction. The company should be aware of what the customers want. This will have a great impact on business growth.

Most business entrepreneurs believe that Covid-19 is not a distraction when it comes to running a business, instead, it is a challenge that will help them to create marketing strategies that are suited for the new normal situation. This supports the study of Jeff Raymond, (April 2020) it tells that disruptors such as the coronavirus were not even considered when marketing plans were created. However, marketers are well-suited to assist in dealing with the business issues that the pandemic has created. When you choose to be a marketer, especially for those who are new to the business industry, they should know that lots of things could happen in the flow of the business. This will test the marketers how well they handle things accordingly that will result in a successful outcome. A conscious evaluation of the 4Ps of marketing is a useful tool for ensuring that your marketing strategy stays on track. Effective marketing strategies would be a great help in this time of the pandemic.

When the COVID-19 pandemic arose, some milk tea shops increased their sales. Which means it is beneficial for them to run their business in the midst of a pandemic. These are the milk tea shops that still have dine-in options and online deliveries. It supports the study of Nina Trentmann and Mark Maurer (2020), it states that Mr. Profumo said, "Customers want their meals wherever, whenever,". It is convenient to the customers because it is less effort to go outside and much safer.

Arne Maas (May 2020) states in his study that it would be an understatement to say that COVID-19 has changed consumer behaviour. But how much and for how long our habits have altered is unknown. When it comes to strategic planning, marketers are left on uncertain ground. There has already been a global transition from reaction to recovery to resilience. During this transformation, some businesses will succeed while others will struggle. Some businesses come up with effective marketing strategies but some are not. It is all about how much effort you will exert for you to manage what is the best for your business, what could be other solutions that make the business still profitable.

The best foundation for any new marketing mix is solid behavioural insights. Businesses should investigate how COVID-19's severe change of context has resulted in a change in customer purchasing behaviours. Whether consciously or unconsciously, they will rethink their actions. The current crisis has created a significant change in the environment, and many of the traditional cues for making decisions have gone. For businesses, this opens up possibilities because consumers are more open to possibilities right now, each of the 4Ps can assist direct them to your products. You can more confidently adapt your 4Ps to a newly disruptive situation if you understand your customers' decisions. Here are some points to consider about 4Ps:

Product - Many businesses have placed on hold long-term innovation ambitions to focus on "in-the-moment" projects that address current customer requirements. It's important to think about possible innovation opportunities in response to behavioural alterations as we prepare for a recovery period — and following the recession.

Place - The increase in online shopping and social media usage has sped up. However, producing a "forced trial" of new online buying behaviour for particular categories, countries, and target customers.

Price - Portfolio pricing will certainly be affected by modern situations and behaviours. Long-held beliefs may be thrown out the window. Begin by segmenting (new and loyal) customers, then consider how they buy now, how their situation has changed, and what choices they're considering.

Promotion - Advertising may aim to reinforce customer loyalty by increasing social media involvement, depending on where consumers are in their decision-making process. It may also be required to initiate an action, such as repeat or trial purchases across multiple channels.

While some industries are struck worse than others, disruption provides an opportunity to adapt and respond to new market opportunities. This study tells how to consider marketing strategies with the same rule of the marketing mix (4Ps) during the pandemic.

People spend a lot of time on social media sites. Through social networking sites, users can communicate and socialize with one another. It is a chance for business owners to promote their company online to increase viral marketing and brand awareness. In the midst of a pandemic, companies should prioritize everyone's health, which is a good marketing strategy to consider.

With this, a firm must concentrate on planning good marketing strategies and making their customers satisfied considering the whole situation in the midst of a pandemic. It is because they are the number one factor to consider in running a business. Thinking about what's the best customer is the first step to know these marketing strategies. Success in making this will be profitable in the side of the business as they gain the trust of their customers and will motivate their customers to consume their products or services. In this time of pandemic thinking creatively, applying safety, and coming up with some solution will let businesses grow and be successful.

3. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, setting of the study, subject of the study, data gathering procedures, and sources of data.

Research Design

The researchers used the descriptive type of quantitative research design, where researchers made closed-ended questions. It is to investigate the effectiveness of marketing strategies in different milk tea shops during a pandemic. Researchers used purposive sampling, a type of Non-probability sampling design to select the respondents of the study. To achieve the purpose of the study, a Descriptive research method will be used to gather all data that will be analysed, classify and tabulate data, and describe the nature of the object that helps the study in the interpretation of its results.

Research Locale

The researcher's study is to be conducted in the area of Molino, Bacoor City wherein different milk tea shops are established. The selected milk tea shops to be covered in this study are Felicitea, Doodle Tea, and Teacarus that operate for more than a year. It is a good place to conduct the study because Molino, Bacoor City is the province's gateway to Manila. More residential communities are being built. This means lots of micro-businesses were put up, lots of people will explore to experience the services of these businesses such as milk tea shops.

Participants of the study

With different Milk tea shops in Molino, Bacoor City, the participants of this study will be their selected 100 customers of the said milk tea shops. Respondents will be asked to answer an online survey questionnaire. We decided to use the Google forms in consideration of our situation where limited people are only allowed to go outside. Researchers will use purposive sampling in selecting the participants. FORMULA was used to identify the number of participants. Purposive sampling was chosen because researchers only want participants who will be able to provide us with the information we require. These participants who experienced the products and services of the selected milk tea shops will contribute to know the effectiveness of marketing mix strategies in the midst of the pandemic. Participants should be willing to cooperate in achieving the purpose of our study.

Research Instrument

The researchers will use Likert and Nominal scale model survey questionnaires as data-gathering instruments. It is a type of rating scale that is used to assess opinions. The Likert method is a type of psychometric scale that is commonly used by researchers to learn about participants' behaviour regarding the study. For a clearer understanding, researchers used 5 point Likert scale: (5) Very Satisfied; (4) Somewhat Satisfied; (3) Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied; (2) Somewhat Dissatisfied; (1) Very Dissatisfied to figure out the level of respondents' satisfaction to the said milk-tea shops. While Nominal scale is a measurement system that is used to categorize events into discrete groups. This scale does not require the use of numeric values; instead, each different category is labelled with a unique identity. Furthermore, it helps to identify the effectiveness of marketing strategies. Researchers decided to use this method to assess the data that are gathered.

Data Gathering Procedures

Researchers' data gathering will be concluded this year September 2021 by conducting this study among different Milk tea shops in the area of Molino Bacoor City Cavite. Researchers did a pre-testing of surveys to approximately 21 people

to improve the research. These pre-testing surveys contributed to the research. The researchers had allotted vigorous time, effort, and cooperation in developing their questionnaire to serve its intended respondents. Online surveys are safe and secure to conduct. As there is no in-person interaction or any direct form of communication, they are quite useful in times of the COVID-19 pandemic. The researchers decided to send the survey questionnaire to people who have access to the internet and are qualified to the criteria set by the researchers where they should have experienced the product and services, cooperative and able to provide the needed information. Researchers will post their survey questionnaires through their social media. The survey was created by relating to the statement of the problem of the research and by the support of individual questions formed by the researchers. In the questionnaire, Likert and nominal scale were used to determine what kind of milk tea shops they like and to identify if the respondents agreed or disagreed with the statements. After the questionnaire was formed, researchers consulted a statistician for advice for better data treatment and analysis. After the professor approves the questionnaire, Google forms will be distributed to one (1) hundred selected participants online. Researchers decided to have a bigger sampling size for the researchers to have a better statistical analysis. When they are done answering, researchers will then thank them for participating in our study. Later, Responses will be collected and will be analysed based on the data treatment and analysis of the study. The purpose of data treatment and analysis of the study is to make broad conclusions regarding the chosen study that is conducted. As a response, researchers will assess the data by weighing all of the information that has been gathered through online surveys.

Data Treatment and Analysis

The researchers will use quantitative research and descriptive statistics, this method helps to determine the general trend in the study. The researchers used statistical tools which are to come to a clear conclusion on this study; frequency and percentage, measures of central tendency, particularly the mean and chi-square are used to examine the data and frequency tables.

Frequency and percentage, simply mean and chi-square was utilized to determine the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the midst of a pandemic of the milk tea shops in the Molino area of Bacoor City Cavite.

Frequency and percentage is a display of data that shows the number of observations for a group of data points in percentages.

To find the frequency and percentage, divide the frequency by the total number of results and multiply by 100.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

The mean is commonly used as an average for every category. This method also has the advantage of being simple and quick to calculate.

To find the mean, add all of the numbers in a set, then divide the sum by the total count of numbers.

Formula:

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\text{Sum of all values in the data set}}{\text{Total no. of values in the data set}}$$

The Chi-square test is commonly used for determining if two categorical variables are related. The Chi-Square test's null hypothesis is that the categorical variables in the population have no connection; they are independent.

To determine the significant relationship between the profile and the variables of the respondents and their perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the midst of pandemic in milk tea shops in Molino Area of Bacoor City Cavite, Chi-square formula was utilized:

Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where:

χ^2 = chi-squared

O_i = observed value

E_i = expected value

For the statistical analysis that they have gathered, the researchers tallied the number of times a certain variable appeared in a category and calculated its percentage.

Using the formula and frequency table that is further elaborated, data are quantified throughout the results and discussion for a clear understanding of how the study's quantitative information is presented.

The researchers will thoroughly quantify and analyse the information gathered. Researchers were confident that the study would be successful if the right data analysis procedures were followed.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

1.1 age;

Frequencies for 1.1 Age		
1.1 Age	Frequency	Percent
1 - 16 years old – 20 years old	33	33
2 - 21 years old – 30 years old	48	48
3 - 31 years old - 40 years old	10	10
4 - 41 years old – 50 years old	7	7
5 - 51 years old – 59 years old	1	1
6 - 60 years old – and above	1	1
Total	100	100

The table shows that out of 100 respondents, most of them are age between 21-30 years old with a percentage of 48%. There are also 33 respondents are 16-20 years old, 10 respondents are between 31-40 years old, and 7 respondents are between 41-70 years old. There are only 1 respondent each who ages between 51-59 years old and 60 years old and above.

1.2 gender;

Frequencies for 1.2 Gender		
1.2 Gender	Frequency	Percent
1 - Female	57	57
2 - Male	43	43
Total	100	100

As per table above, it shows that 57% of the respondents are female, and the remaining 43% with a frequency of 43 are male.

1.3 civil status;

Frequencies for 1.3 Civil Status		
1.3 Civil Status	Frequency	Percent
1 - Single	81	81
2 - Married	19	19
Total	100	100

Out of 100 % of the respondents, the 81% with a frequency of 81 are single, and the rest 19% are married.

1.4 educational attainment;

Frequencies for 1.4 Educational Attainment		
1.4 Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
1 - High school Graduate	36	36
2 - Vocational/Associate Degree	12	12
3 - College Graduate	35	35
4 - Post Graduate	17	17
Total	100	100

The table shows that the majority of the respondents are High school graduate, with a 36% out of 100% of the respondents. While 35% are College graduate, 17% are Post graduate, and the remaining 12% of 100 respondents have a Vocational/Associate Degree.

1.5 income /allowance;

Frequencies for 1.5 Income/Allowance		
1.5 Income/Allowance	Frequency	Percent
1 - ₱1,000 – ₱3,000	39	39
2 - ₱3,001 – ₱ 5 ,000	9	9
3 - ₱5,001 – ₱ 10,000	11	11
4 - ₱10,001 - ₱ 20,000	20	20
5 - ₱20,001 – UP	21	21
Total	100	100

The data above shows that in 100 respondents there are 21 respondents have a monthly income of ₱20,001 – UP, 20 respondents have ₱10,001 - ₱ 20,000 monthly income/allowance, another 11 respondents have ₱5,001 – ₱ 10,000 income/allowance, and only 9 respondents have ₱3,001 – ₱ 5, 000. While majority of the respondents with a frequency of 39 have ₱1,000 – ₱3,000 monthly income/allowance.

1.6 frequency

Frequencies for Frequency eat in a Milk tea shop		
Frequency eat in a Milk tea shop	Frequency	Percent
1 - Always	28	28
2 - Sometimes	44	44
3 - Seldom	28	28
Total	100	100

As per table above, it indicates how frequently the respondents visited the Milk tea shop, and it shows that out of 100 respondents, 28 respondents always eat in a Milk tea shop, and another 28 respondents eat in a Milk tea shop infrequently. While, majority of the respondents, which is 44 of them answered they sometimes eat at Milk tea shop.

2. What is the perception of the customers on the marketing mix components as to:

2.1 Product;

Product	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q1.1 Menu	4.11	Somewhat Satisfied
Q1.2 Taste	4.38	Somewhat Satisfied
Q1.3 Food Variety	4.27	Somewhat Satisfied
Q1.4 Product Bundles	4.26	Somewhat Satisfied
Q1.5 Different flavours of Milk Tea	4.38	Somewhat Satisfied
Overall Perception on Product	4.28	High

The table above shows the mean and verbal interpretation of sub questions under Product. Q1.1 has the lowest mean with 4.11 and verbal interpretation of Somewhat Satisfied. Q1.2 and Q1.5 both have the highest mean with 4.38 and Somewhat

Satisfied verbal interpretation. While Q1.3 have 4.27 mean and also have verbal interpretation Somewhat Satisfied as well as Q1.4 with 4.26 mean. Overall, the perception on Product has 4.28 mean and high verbal interpretation.

2.2 Price;

Price	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
q.2.1 Prices of the product when offering online	4.5	Very Satisfied
Q2.2 Delivery Fee	4.4	Somewhat Satisfied
Q2.3 Bundle Pricing	4.34	Somewhat Satisfied
Q2.4 Affordable Price	4.48	Somewhat Satisfied
Q2.5 Purchased Product with more Lower Value Price	4.19	Somewhat Satisfied
Overall Perception on Price	4.382	High

As shown in the table above are the mean and verbal interpretation of sub questions under Price. Q2.4 has 4.48 mean, followed by Q2.2 with 4.4 mean, Q2.3 with 4.34 mean, and Q2.5 with a lowest mean of 4.19. All of these have Somewhat Satisfied verbal interpretation. However, Q2.1 has Very Satisfied verbal interpretation with a highest mean of 4.5. Overall, the perception on Price has High verbal interpretation with 4.382 mean.

2.3 Place;

Place	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q3.1 Ambiance	4.26	Somewhat Satisfied
Q3.2 Area Space	4.05	Somewhat Satisfied
Q3.3 Social Distancing Inside the Store	4.26	Somewhat Satisfied
Q3.4 Disinfect and Clean work spaces	4.32	Somewhat Satisfied
Q3.5 Change of Size in Recent Years	4.32	Somewhat Satisfied
Overall Perception on Place	4.242	High

As per table above, the perception on Place has High verbal interpretation with 4.242 mean. Q3.1 has 4.26 mean, Q3.2 has 4.05 mean, Q3.3 has 4.26 mean, and both Q3.4 and Q3, 5 has 4.32 mean. All sub questions have Somewhat Satisfied verbal interpretation.

2.4 Promotion

Promotion	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Q4.1 Online Ordering Application	4.32	Somewhat Satisfied
Q4.2 Good Customer Services	4.41	Somewhat Satisfied
Q4.3 Giving the clients the ability to Order, pay for and Collect their Beverages without waiting in line	4.42	Somewhat Satisfied
Q4.4 Promos and Discount Coupons	4.33	Somewhat Satisfied
Q4.5 Free Delivery (If each minimum orders required)	4.34	Somewhat Satisfied
Overall Perception on promotion	4.364	High

As per table above, it shows the mean and verbal interpretation of sub questions under Promotion. Q4.1 has the lowest mean with 4.32 and Somewhat Satisfied verbal interpretation, while Q4.3 has the highest mean with 4.42, and Somewhat Satisfied verbal interpretation. Followed by Q4.2 with 4.41 mean, Q4.5 with 4.34 mean, and Q4.4 with 4.33 mean with verbal interpretation of Somewhat Satisfied. Overall, the perception on Promotion has 4.364 mean with High verbal interpretation.

3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their perception in the effectiveness of marketing strategies during Pandemic in Fast Food Restaurants in Molino Area of Bacoor City Cavite?

Perception and Age	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Product	4.663	0.324	Not Significant
Price	2.223	0.695	Not Significant
Place	0.756	0.944	Not Significant
Promotion	2.921	0.571	Not Significant
Overall Perception	1.909	0.752	Not Significant

Interpretation:

There is no significant relationship between the respondents Age and their perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, specifically, the perception on Product, price, place and promotion, since the chi-square values of 4.663, 2.223, 0.756, and 2.921 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that age does not affect the perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, in terms of Product, price, place and promotion.

Also. There is no significant relationship between the respondents Age and their overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, since the chi-square value of 1.909 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that age does not affect the overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City.

Perception and Gender	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Product	2.170	0.338	Not Significant
Price	0.311	0.856	Not Significant
Place	0.799	0.671	Not Significant
Promotion	2.261	0.323	Not Significant
Overall Perception	3.606	0.165	Not Significant

Interpretation:

There is no significant relationship between the respondents' gender and their perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, specifically, the perception on Product, price, place and promotion, since the chi-square values of 2.170, 0.311, 0.799 and 2.261 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that gender does not affect the perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, in terms of Product, price, place and promotion.

Also. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' gender and their overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, since the chi-square value of 3.606 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that gender does not affect the overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City.

Perception and Civil Status	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Product	2.415	0.299	Not Significant
Price	1.472	0.479	Not Significant
Place	0.973	0.615	Not Significant
Promotion	3.842	0.146	Not Significant
Overall Perception	0.822	0.663	Not Significant

Interpretation:

There is no significant relationship between the respondents' civil status and their perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, specifically, the perception on Product, price, place and promotion, since the chi-square values of 2.415, 1.472, 0.973 and 3.843 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that civil status does not affect the perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, in terms of Product, price, place and promotion.

Also. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' civil status and their overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, since the chi-square value of 0.822 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that civil status does not affect the overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City.\

Perception and Educational Attainment	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Product	4.485	0.611	Not Significant
Price	1.758	0.941	Not Significant
Place	7.023	0.319	Not Significant
Promotion	6.238	0.397	Not Significant
Overall Perception	3.236	0.779	Not Significant

Interpretation:

There is no significant relationship between the respondents' educational attainment and their perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, specifically, the perception on Product, price, place and promotion, since the chi-square values of 4.485, 1.758, 7.023 and 6.238 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that educational attainment does not affect the perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, in terms of Product, price, place and promotion.

Also. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' educational attainment and their overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, since the chi-square value of 3.236 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that educational attainment does not affect the overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City.

Perception and Income/Allowance	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Product	9.820	0.132	Not Significant
Price	9.306	0.157	Not Significant
Place	6.226	0.398	Not Significant
Promotion	5.957	0.428	Not Significant
Overall Perception	2.823	0.831	Not Significant

Interpretation:

There is no significant relationship between the respondents' income/allowance and their perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, specifically, the perception on Product, price, place and promotion, since the chi-square values of 9.820, 9.306, 6.226 and 5.957 have p-values greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that income/allowance does not affect the perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, in terms of Product, price, place and promotion.

Also. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' income/allowance and their overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, since the chi-square value of 2.823 has a p-value greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that income/allowance does not affect the overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City.

Perception and Frequency of Visit/Eat	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Product	32.139	<0.001	Significant
Price	34.133	<0.001	Significant
Place	18.781	<0.001	Significant
Promotion	35.073	<0.001	Significant
Overall Perception	52.479	<0.001	Significant

Interpretation:

There is a significant relationship between the respondents' frequency of visit/eat and their perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, specifically, the perception on Product, price, place and promotion, since the chi-square values of 32.139, 34.133, 18.781 and 35.073 have p-values less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship were rejected. This indicated that frequency of visit/eat affect the perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, in terms of Product, price, place and promotion; The higher the frequency of visit the lower will be the perception and vice versa.

Also. There is a significant relationship between the respondents' frequency of visit/eat and their overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City, since the chi-square value 52.479 has a p-value less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship was rejected. This indicated that frequency of visit/eat affect the overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies during the pandemic in Milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City,; The higher the frequency of visit the lower will be the overall perception and vice versa.

5. CONCLUSION

The study is about the Effectiveness of Marketing Strategies in the Midst of Pandemic in the Customers of Milk Tea Shops in Molino II of Bacoor City Cavite. The researchers conducted the study to assess the effectiveness of the marketing strategies of milk tea shops in the midst of the pandemic. Thus, to determine the significant relationship among the variables. With the use of the chi-square formula, researchers measured the perception of the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the midst of pandemic in the customers of milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City Cavite.

In synthesizing the results of the study, the survey has a total of 100 respondents. We have a demographic profile divided into categories which are age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, monthly income/allowance and frequency of visit. In terms of age, the results show that the highest percentage was at the ages of 21–30 years old with a total percentage of 48% out of 100 participants. Researchers concluded that 21-30 years of age are mostly the customers who usually go to milk tea shops. On gender, the majority of the respondents who took the survey are female with a total of 57 participants out of 100 equivalent to 57%. In terms of civil status, most of the respondents are single with a total of 81%. Most of the respondents are high school graduates with 36% and college graduates with 35%. Most of their monthly income ranges from 1,000 to 3,000 pesos. The frequency of visits to milk tea shops is sometimes, with a total percentage of 44%. In this part of the study, researchers concluded that most of the participants are all in middle age. The data gathered are very helpful, especially to those people who are planning to go outside and eat at milk tea shops in this time of the pandemic. Moreover, the researchers conclude that the overall perception of the customers on the marketing mix components as per Product, Place, Promotion and Price are all high.

Furthermore, based on the findings the researchers conclude that the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of age, gender, civil status, educational attainment and income/allowance has no significant relationship with their overall perceptions on the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the midst of pandemic in the customers of milk tea shops in Molino II of Bacoor City Cavite. Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship was not rejected. This indicated that the demographic profile of respondents does not affect the overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the midst of pandemic in the customers of milk tea shops. However, the demographic profile in terms of frequency of visit has a significant relationship with their overall perception on the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the midst of pandemic in the customers of milk tea shops. This indicates that frequency of visit/eat affects the overall perception in the marketing strategies of milk tea shops and is favourable to the customers as it fulfils their satisfaction. Customer satisfaction will lead to a strong relationship between the company and customers, and it will also increase the customer loyalty to the company, with this, it will create a positive public image which contributes to good brand equity and aids in business growth.

Overall, marketing is essential in the business world, and customers are the most important part of it. Now, in the midst of a pandemic, there are different marketing strategies that are really effective. These strategies will help the company continue to increase sales and secure the safety of customers while providing service. This study can help those who are about to start small businesses such as milk tea shops to know furthermore about marketing strategies' effectiveness in the new normal. It highlights the change of marketing strategies to fulfil customers' needs and wants.

6. RECOMMENDATION

For the recommendations of the study, this part will tackle all the possible suggestions to improve the Effectiveness of Marketing Strategies in the Midst of Pandemic in the Customers of Milk Tea Shops in Molino II of Bacoor City Cavite.

- In promoting the product and company of the business while in the midst of a pandemic, a good marketing strategy is to enter e-commerce in promoting the product. This will serve as a great help to improve the marketing strategies since some people are afraid to go outside due to the continuous spreading of viruses.
- The use of social media has a significant influence on how goods and services are advertised online.

- The consumer's purchase decision is influenced by pricing. Consumers are increasingly concerned with price considering the need to save money, and they are equally concerned with product quality to guarantee that their money is not wasted.
- It is also necessary to have more space for a larger table that can accommodate a group of people.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cahiles, B. (June 2020). Dine-in restaurants, fastfood allowed in MGCQ. Retrieved from https://mb-com-ph.cdn.ampproject.org/v/s/mb.com.ph/2020/06/01/dine-in-restaurants-fastfood-allowed-in-mgcq/?amp_js_v=a6&_gsa=1&&usqp=mq331AQKKAFQArABIIACAw%3D%3D&fbclid=IwAR2ZgBz8KRsrblGoAQI5rJgeUEEGl4nnI8z7ffvRhtCHJ1D7usweeY8CNHc#aoh=16250731371640&referrer=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com&_tf=From%20%251%24s&share=https%3A%2F%2Fmb.com.ph%2F2020%2F06%2F01%2Fdine-in-restaurants-fastfood-allowed-in-mgcq%2F
- [2] Chen, LS., Chen, WK., Riantama, D. (2020). Using a Text Mining Approach to Hear Voices of Customers from Social Media toward the Fast-Food Restaurant Industry. Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/1/268/htm>
- [3] Ehmke, C., Fulton, J., Lusk, J. (n.d). Marketing's Four P's: First Steps for New Entrepreneurs. Retrieved from <https://www.extension.purdue.edu/extmedia/ec/ec-730.pdf>
- [4] Kirby, L., McCarthy, T., Moorman, C., Shkil, B. (2020). 5 Marketing Strategies and Missed Opportunities During COVID-19. Retrieved from <https://www.ama.org/marketing-news/5-marketing-opportunities-in-the-covid-19-era/>
- [5] Maas, A. (2020). A post-COVID-19 strategy means getting back to basics with the 4Ps: product, price, place, and promotion. Retrieved from https://www.foodbeverageinsider.com/market-trends-analysis/its-time-consider-your-post-covid-marketing-strategy?fbclid=IwAR0l_wVgB2ualmoomY3Zive2JVgKWSt-X8eHnjKTplu5sDanelktx-Tc_c
- [6] Maurer, M., Trentmann N. (2020). Fast-Food Chains See Shifts Made During Pandemic Paying Off. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com.ph/amp/s/www.wsj.com/amp/articles/fast-food-chains-see-shifts-made-during-pandemic-paying-off-11596032316>
- [7] Morgan et al. (2019). Research in marketing strategy. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science. Pp. 34. Retrieved from <https://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/136066/1/JAMS%20Final%20Version%20Unblinded.pdf>
- [8] Purwanto, P. (2021). Recovery Marketing Strategy for Custom Bag Producer-Home Industry During the Covid-19 Pandemic. Vol. 5, Issue. 2. Retrieved from <http://jurnal.stie-aas.ac.id/index.php/IJEBAR/article/view/2304/1088>
- [9] Reymond, J. (2020). The 4Ps of Marketing Amid COVID-19: Strategy Reassessment and Adjustment. Retrieved from https://www.marketingprofs.com/articles/2020/42801/the-4ps-of-marketing-amid-covid-19-strategy-reassessment-and-adjustment?fbclid=IwAR04OdUmp--Llnu8fXmfl1zpegabM3QOmZ_2ckF9RqXVcNWwHSv8Iks2oVE